

Answers to Pre-Draft Questions: “Séance Serenade”

The purpose of this piece is to be an entertaining musical commentary on the inherent satirical humor of performing works of music by long dead composers. The audience for this piece will generally be individuals involved with new music but there is the potential for this work to reach a broader audience of the general concert music enthusiast. The goal is for the work to be found humorous and serve as a starting point for individual reflection on the impact of repeated programming of historical music that no longer speaks to the culture and society of today. This piece will try to impress upon the audience this idea through performative metaphor; if it is accepted that performers act as a conduit for a composer’s voice, then performing music from composers that have long passed away is effectively allowing the dead to speak. This piece plans to accomplish this through a satirical rendering of a stylized 19th-century french séance where the soprano is then possessed in turn by Verdi, Mozart, and Gounoud. Musically, the piece will pull from arias by these composers - actually incorporating quotation in the sections of full possession - and intertwine those musical aesthetics with those of modernists such as Berio and Aperghis; while also incorporating to extent the techniques of horror film scores, to evoke the frightening scene of a possession. The full positions should serve as such a strong and unexpected musical contrast that the subversion of expectation on such a scale should cause intentional laughter in the audience.

The piece will be performed by a trio of Soprano, Bass Clarinet, and Percussion. The soprano will serve as the theatrical leader of the séance, and will be the conduit through which the audience experiences the ideas of possession. She will be seated at a small table with a false ouija board. The bass clarinetist and the percussionist will start off seated at the table, early in the piece move to outward stations where their instruments are set, and return to the small table without instruments at the end of the piece. The bass clarinetist and percussionist create the “music in atmosphere”, they are not narrative characters but rather musical participants and create sound to enhance the core feeling in any given moment of the piece being conveyed to the audience. Ideally this piece will showcase both the full spectrum of expressive ability available to a lyrical coloratura soprano - from staple arias to modern and extended techniques - as well as the percussion and bass clarinet who will playing jarring material in between possessions and uncanny valley accompaniment in the moments where the soprano is fully possessed.

The piece will be 8 - 12 minutes long. It will have a form of 3 possession “episodes”, consisting of a spirit entering the soprano (horror), the soprano becoming fully possessed (quotation) and then a groove section where the soprano battles to free themselves of the spirit and the two musical pools are mixed. These 3 episodes will be bookended by interaction by all 3 performers with a false ouija board (tapping, slapping, moving of the planchette). These sections will provide initial suspense and intrigue as well as formal closure.